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Short Communication

An Open Letter to the 2022 Winners of the Nobel Prize in Physics

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Abstract

The theoretical concept of photonic quantum nonlocality cannot be implemented physically because of the quantum Rayleigh scattering of single photons. A distinction needs to be made between the correlation of individual, single measurements of pure states and the correlation of the *measured ensembles of mixed states*. The correlation operator of Pauli vector operators delivers the same probabilities of correlated detections of photons for both independent and multi-photon states as for 'entangled' states of photons. As single-photon sources are not needed, the design and implementation of quantum computing operations and other devices will be significantly streamlined.

About two years ago, the 2022 Nobel Prize in Physics elevated the concept of quantum nonlocality from a possibility to a certainty. Recent background briefing articles [1,2] reveal significant difficulties in the implementation of practical quantum computers based on the concepts of entangled states and quantum nonlocality-related correlations of detected single photons despite heavy resources having been invested in the last two decades. This is not surprising given the omissions of quantum physical processes and physical contradictions that have been allowed to persist in the professional literature of leading journals. Many physical aspects and processes have been omitted from the theory of Quantum Optics for reasons of expediency. Some of these missing elements are listed below.

Published experimental results in other journals than Physical Review Letters, have reported quantum-strong correlations with independent photons [3,4] based on polarization measurements for both the CHSH and the CH Bell inequalities. These results are consistent with the expansion of the Pauli vector correlation operator used by Bell in 1964, i.e., $\hat{c} = (\mathbf{a} \cdot \hat{\sigma})(\mathbf{b} \cdot \hat{\sigma})$ leading to an identity operator multiplied by the correlation function, i.e., the operator \hat{c} can be reduced to [5]; Eq. (A6):

$$\hat{c} = (\mathbf{a} \cdot \hat{\sigma})(\mathbf{b} \cdot \hat{\sigma}) = \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b} \hat{I} + i (\mathbf{a} \times \mathbf{b}) \cdot \hat{\sigma} \quad (1)$$

where the linear polarization unit vectors \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} identify the orientations of the detecting polarization filters in the

Stokes representation, and $\hat{\sigma} = (\hat{\sigma}_1, \hat{\sigma}_2, \hat{\sigma}_3)$ is the Pauli spin vector (with $\hat{\sigma}_2 = i \hat{\sigma}_1 \hat{\sigma}_3$). The presence of the identity operator in Eq. (1) implies that, when the last term vanishes for a linear polarization state, the correlation function is determined by the orientations of the polarization filters, for any type of quantum state, even non-entangled ones [6]. *This physical aspect should have been known to J. Bell in 1964 and his followers for the last six decades, and would have saved a great deal of misguided research.*

A single photon is deflected from a straight-line propagation in a dielectric medium by the quantum Rayleigh scattering [7]. Groups of identical photons can propagate in a straight line through stimulated Rayleigh emission [8,9]. The spontaneously emitted photons in the nonlinear crystal undergo parametric amplification forming a group of identical photons. This group of photons can overcome the quantum Rayleigh scattering through quantum Rayleigh stimulated emission (QRStE) [8,9]. The effect of QRStE plays a critical role in creating groups of identical photons in a commonly used dielectric beam splitter as explained in ref. [9]. This physical aspect should have been known for the last four decades and should have saved a great deal of misguided research.

There is no experimental evidence of a single photon propagating in a straight line inside a dielectric medium. The nonlinear crystal that generates parametrically the original pair of photons also amplifies the single photons into groups

of identical photons. These groups of photons can propagate in a straight line inside a dielectric medium but they do not comply with the conditions of quantum nonlocality.

The 2015 landmark experiments [10,11] reported a very low probability of coincident detections of a mere 0.0002 (2×10^{-4}) with one setting at each of the two stations, the overall outcomes being fitted with highly non-entangled states of photons, thereby disproving any claim of quantum nonlocality despite the common view [12].

The effect of quantum nonlocality is meant to synchronize the detections recorded at the two locations A and B for polarization-entangled states of photons. In the caption [12], on its second page, one reads: "...if both polarizers are aligned along the same direction ($a = b$), then the results of A and B will be either (+1; +1) or (-1; -1) but never (+1; -1) or (-1; +1.); this is a total correlation as can be determined by measuring the four rates with the fourfold detection circuit." Yet, the quantum correlation is supposed to take place at the level of each pair of entangled photons rather than between averaged values of the two distributions; but such an outcome has **never** been reported, which fact was ignored in ref. [12] as well as in the 2022 Nobel Prize citation.

The reproducibility of experimental results is a fundamental principle of science. The two separate detectors are identical and operated under identical conditions. Consequently, they will produce identical distributions of measured outcomes, regardless of the type of photons, but with different sequential orders.

Our question to A. Aspect, A. Zeilinger and J. Clauser:

How can a single photon avoid photon-dipole interactions of absorption and re-emission given the Avogadro number of $6.02214076 \times 10^{23}$ of atoms per mole? Otherwise, no synchronized detections of the initial pair of photons are possible, ruling out any effect of quantum nonlocality.

The alleged quantum effect of nonlocality is meant to operate between two photons of the original 'entangled'-pair of photons. However, the proven, but, intentionally ignored, process of quantum Rayleigh scattering prevents any synchronization of two separate detections. Consequently, the 2022 Nobel Prize in Quantum Physics must be suspended for the sake of scientific integrity and credibility.

The physically meaningful interpretations of the experiments are available in ref. [13].

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